

Geochemistry of Devonian ophiolites from NW Iberian Massif: the record of an evolving ephemeral oceanic basin.

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The section of the Variscan Orogen represented at the Iberian Massif preserves several ophiolitic sequences from which the Devonian types have been most controversial regarding their interpretation. Initially considered the remnants of the Rheic Ocean, formed during its closure by intraoceanic subduction (Sánchez Martínez et al. 2007), after more detailed studies of their geochemical features including whole rock and isotope geochemistry of the mafic assemblages, as well as the characterization of the adjacent metamorphic terranes, they were reinterpreted as an ephemeral oceanic basin opened at the most external margin of Gondwana, after developing of a first high-pressure event consequence of its collision with Laurussia (Arenas et al. 2014a, b).

The representatives of these Devonian ophiolites located at the allochthonous complexes of NW Iberia are the Careón, Purrido and Moeche ophiolites. All of them occupy an intermediate position within the allochthonous nappes, sandwiched between metamorphic terranes of continental affinity, the basal units below and the upper units on top of them. The Careón Ophiolite located at SE of the Órdenes Complex is the thickest sequence, consisting of a stack of three tectonic slices where ultramafic and gabbroic sections can be distinguished. Abundant diabase dikes intrude both sections, which together with the absence of volcanic members differentiates this ophiolite from the typical "Penrose" assemblage. The Purrido and Moeche ophiolites belong to the Cabo Ortegal Complex, although the contact between them might not seem evident because Purrido crops out to the W and Moeche to the E of the allochthonous complex. However, the sheared base of Purrido resembles the most typical lithologies of Moeche, which leads to interpret that Moeche Ophiolite occupies a position below Purrido Ophiolite. These ophiolites are less varied regarding their lithological composition, being constituted mostly by amphibolites, in the case of Purrido, and mylonitic greenschists with some alternations of ultramafic and micaschists in the case of Moeche. The chronology of the three units has been dated at ca. 400 Ma by U-Pb method in zircons by different authors and laboratories (Díaz García et al. 1999, Pin et al. 2002, Sánchez Martínez et al. 2011, Arenas et al. 2014a). There is also evidence for a zircon source of ca. 1160 Ma recorded in a sample of Purrido Ophiolite (Sánchez Martínez et al. 2006), which agrees with the old/crustal ϵ_{Hf} signature of the zircons from mylonitic greenschists of the Moeche Unit (Arenas et al. 2014a). These facts were key to discard the origin of this oceanic basin as result of intraoceanic subduction.

The whole rock geochemical features of these three ophiolitic sequences, although being described separately in previous works, have not yet been considered as a whole with the aim of reconstructing the evolution of the Devonian basin. The whole set of data available and the reassignment of some of the samples to other ophiolitic unit (i.e. sheared metabasites from the bottom of Purrido Ophiolite now classified as samples from the Moeche Ophiolite) provide a picture of the different sections of the same oceanic basin, now dismembered and distributed along the allochthonous terranes of NW Iberia. When plotting the immobile trace

element contents of the most representative mafic lithologies of each ophiolitic sequence (gabbros and dikes of basaltic/andesitic-basaltic composition from Careón, Purrido amphibolites and Moeche greenschists both of basaltic composition) normalized to the N-MORB composition from Sun & McDonough (1984), the most significant feature they display is the negative Ta-Nb anomaly indicative of settings associated with subduction zones. Nevertheless, such anomaly is more marked in Careón samples than in Purrido amphibolites and even more attenuated in Moeche greenschists. The trace element patterns of the three ophiolites transition from slightly fractionated to almost flat or N-MORB like, indicating that the influence of the subduction decreases from the ophiolite stacked in the highest position (Careón Ophiolite) to the lowest (Moeche Ophiolite). The same trend is also evidenced plotting the samples at the Th/Yb vs. Nb/Yb diagram from Pearce (2014), based on the Th/Nb proxy that monitors subduction/crustal input. While the greenschist samples from Moeche Ophiolite plot within the MORB array resembling N-MORB compositions, Purrido amphibolites drift toward higher Th/Yb ratios and Careón samples plot above the MORB array, indicating a stronger input from the subduction zone. The interpretation of these data indicates that each of the Devonian ophiolites might represent a different part of a developed suprasubduction basin where the Careón Ophiolite was located closest to the trench in the Northest position and Purrido and Moeche ophiolites were the sections progressively farther to the South and less influenced by the subduction activity.

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